

Dynamic citizenship education and argumentative dialogue. A review of concepts and applications

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TEDYC

Toolkit for Educating
to a Dynamic Citizenship

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Introduction

In this literature review, we work on two converging streams of literature that are relevant for our project and complementary. On the one hand, we consider research in political sciences and education that has to do with a dynamic conceptualization of citizenship (Section 1) and with existing tools related to education to a dynamic citizenship (Section 2). These studies have shown the importance of dialogue on controversial issues in the education to a dynamic citizenship. On the other hand, we devote Section 3 to argumentation studies that, on the basis of a conceptualization of argumentative discussion as based on an exchange of arguments aimed at reasonable persuasion, consider education and, more in particular, citizenship education as an important field.

For this literature review, we have used scientific online databases and portals, which collect peer-reviewed scientific articles and empirical evidence. We have referred as well to database, as in the case of Edudoc.ch, which collect institutional documents in the domain of education. Given the strong impetus for promoting citizenship education provided by governmental institutions and organizations at national and international level, reports and recommendations from these sources have also been included in this review.

The languages used for the research are English, French, German, Italian and Spanish with the implementation of the following keywords (see Table 1). We discussed these keywords jointly in the project team; the keywords have been selected on the basis of our knowledge of previous research on citizenship education and argumentation in the field of education (see for example the discussion in Lupatini, 2018, 2021; Greco & Perret-Clermont, 2023)

Table 1: Keywords at the basis of the literature review

English	German	French	Italian	Spanish
Citizenship education	Politische Bildung	Éducation à la citoyenneté	Educazione alla cittadinanza	Educación para la Ciudadanía / educación ciudadana
Civic education	Politische Bildung	Éducation / Instruction civique	Educazione / Istruzione civica	Educación cívica
Civic and citizenship education	Politische Bildung	Éducation civique et à la citoyenneté	Educazione civica e alla cittadinanza	Educación cívica y para la ciudadanía
Democratic education	Demokratische Bildung	Éducation aux valeurs démocratiques	Educazione ai valori democratici	Educación democrática
Democracy education	Demokratiepädagogik	Éducation à la démocratie	Educazione alla democrazia	Educación para la democracia
Dynamic citizenship/education	Dynamische politische Bildung	Éducation à la citoyenneté dynamique	Educazione alla cittadinanza dinamica	Educación para una ciudadanía responsable
Global citizenship education	Globale politische Bildung	Éducation à la citoyenneté mondiale/globale	Educazione alla cittadinanza globale	Educación para la ciudadanía mundial
Digital citizenship education	Digitale politische Bildung	Éducation à la citoyenneté numérique	Educazione alla cittadinanza digitale	Educación para una ciudadanía digital
Human rights education / humanitarian law education	Menschenrechtsbildung	Éducation aux droits de humains et au droit humanitaire	Educazione ai diritti umani / dell'uomo / al diritto umanitario	Educación en derechos humanos / en derecho humanitario
Children rights education	Kinderrechtsbildung	Éducation aux droits de l'enfant	Educazione ai diritti dei bambini / del bambino / dell'infanzia	Educación en derechos de infancia
English	German	French	Italian	Spanish
Toolkit/kit	Toolkit/kit			
Instrument	Gerät / Werkzeug / Instrument	Instrument	Strumento	Instrumento
Simulation play	Simulation	Jeu de simulation	Gioco di simulazione	Juego de simulación
Roleplay	Rollenspiel	Jeu de rôle	Gioco di ruolo	Juego de roles
Business/management play	Planspiel	Jeu de simulation		Juego de simulación
	Planspiel			
Argumentation design AND argumentative design				
Argumentation in the classroom	Argumentation in der Schule	Argumentation à l'école AND argumentation en classe	Argomentazione a scuola	Argumentación en la escuela

Argumentation and civic education	Argumentation und politische Bildung	Argumentation et éducation civique	Argomentazione e educazione civica	Argumentación y educación cívica
Controversy (in the classroom)	?	Enseignement (de) questions controversées	Questioni controverse (a) scuola	
Deliberative platforms				

In order to retrieve these keywords from the selected sources, we have checked titles, abstracts and keywords with no limitation concerning the year of publication. The rationale behind the decision to systematically search in the scientific databases listed above on the basis of jointly discussed keywords is that by so doing, we aimed at a systematic and comprehensive overview of studies concerning the topic of this project. Our aim was to include qualitative/quantitative/mixed studies.

The research has been performed with the aim to pursue following goals:

- Establish an inventory of existing pedagogical tools and toolkits for citizenship education, focusing in particular on those centered on argumentation.
- Report existing measures of their efficacy in short and long term.

1 Training citizenship

Before exploring the existing literature on citizenship education and particularly on the toolkits in use for it, it is relevant to reflect on the concept of citizenship in order to delineate its different meanings, their links with different forms of citizenship education and the different spheres of action. This reflection is the objective of Section 1.1. In the Section 1.2, the attention is concentrated on different institutional solutions adopted to foster citizenship education in different European countries. Further on, Section 1.3 is centered on a reflection on the competencies for educating to the political, in particular the ones to be developed in the projected toolkit.

1.1 Working between politics and the political

The project Toolkit for Educating to a Dynamic Citizenship (TEDYC) aims the planning of a learning/teaching toolkit based on a dynamic conceptualization of citizenship

considered as having many faces and assuming different meanings depending on the context. Citizenship is a polysemous concept, vast and continuously evolving, and “impossible à cerner de façon absolue” (Audigier, 2000, p. 10), it can be considered “as a legal category, as a claim, as an identity, as a tool in nation building, and as an ideal” (Staeheli, 2011, p. 393). It can be perceived and experienced differently by individuals claiming to be citizens of the same space (Yuval-Davis, 2011, pp. 5-6). Depending on the meaning considered, the concrete implications in everyday life are strongly distinguished: it can assume an inclusive or exclusive character, involve active participation or only be a passive state of the person (Watson, 2004). The very concept of participation is polysemic, and divergent opinions emerge on what kind of participation citizenship education should foster. Vote in every election or influence the market by buying and boycotting? Critique political leaders or volunteer in conventional and unconventional manner? Debate with people carrying different opinions or strengthening its own discussing with like-minded people? (Hess, 2009, p. 24).

Despite its polysemy and its fluidity, citizenship is always conceived in relation to a collectivity in the context of an institutional frame (Audigier, 2000, p. 17). The collectivity plays at different levels, and it should not be reduced to the State, but it includes every form of institutionalized community (Yuval-Davis, 2011, p. 6). Audigier (2019, p. 21) and Staeheli (2011, p. 398) define two conceptions of the link between the individual and the collectivity: one static based on a status and inherited (i.e. citizenship expressed through membership in a state), and one dynamic based on decisions and choices, which evolves towards a citizenship centered “autour de la participation, des initiatives citoyennes et du débat” (Audigier et al., 2015, p. 164). A citizenship conceived as dynamic is multi-scalar from the local to the global (Audigier, 2000; Staeheli, 2011, p. 396), it is continuously in evolution, never completely defined (Staeheli, 2011, pp. 398-399), in short it is always in construction, and its education requires the acquirement and the consolidation of competencies (Tutiaux-Guillon, 2006).

Training, forming and educating citizens for the present and for the future helping them to realize that they are part of a set of communities ranging from the narrower at local level to the wider ones at global level, is one of the main tasks of each State, despite of its political form, and it is therefore one of the principal objectives of teaching and learning activities led in schools all over the World at different levels from the Primary School to Institution working at Third Grade (European Commission, 2018). Even long-life learning focuses on these goals, as for instance the long-life learning competences defined by the European Commission and the European Council in 2010 (European Council & Commission, 2010) in particular the sixth competence: “social and civic competences” (European Council & Commission, 2010, p. 2).

This focus on the citizen of today and of tomorrow is present in schools in different cultural, social, spatial, economic and political contexts and is based on the implementation of diversified tools and methods, and on the achievement of a wide range of objectives. Nevertheless, it is important to stress that school is not the unique operator in this field: all associative forms in the civic society as neighborhood committees, trade unions, political parties, local movements and others contribute to achieve this objective. Family plays also an important role in this field. Moreover, it is also relevant to recall that this task does not concern exclusively people of school age, but it touches everyone at every age. Nevertheless, public and inclusive schools play an important role in this domain, and, compared with other educational actors, school has the opportunity to operate in a better structured and solid institutional environment (Biesta, 2012, p. 691).

The formation of citizens of today and of tomorrow has two main objectives, which define its two principal forms:

- transmission of knowledge about the State and the Institutions with the aim to understand their functioning.

– acquirement of the competences necessary to actively take part to the functioning of the State and of the Institutions and to assume an active role in society.

The first objective is mainly achieved by civic instruction, the second one by education for citizenship and for democracy. These should not be considered synonymous, because they refer to different fields, and have different goals. Moreover, they refer to pedagogical approaches based on distinguished contents, methods, objectives and competencies.

Another distinction between civic instruction and citizenship education can be drawn on the basis of the distinction between the German terms *die Politik* und *das Politische*, which can be translated into English with *politics* and *the political* respectively. These two concepts have a common origin: the polis, and more precisely life in common in the polis. To act politically means to act in reference to the polis (Bedorf & Röttgers, 2010, p. 7). The concept of polis does not designate an urban space in its spatial localization and should not be understood in its strict sense of the City-State in Ancient Greece. It indicates preferably an organizational structure developed when people share a space of common life or they meet in action and speech (Arendt, 1960, p. 192).

Despite their common origins, politics and the political indicate two distinct ways of referring to common life in the polis. The political could be defined as an “öffentlicher Erscheinungsraum” (Bedorf, 2010, p. 18) or a “politischer-öffentlicher Raum” (Arendt, 1960, p. 25). The publicity included in the political defines it as the space of the “Allseitigkeit” (Arendt, 2003, p. 96) where different systems of thought, visions, ideologies on the functioning and the goals of common life meet (Bedorf, 2010; Marchart, 2010; Mouffe, 2005; Weißeno et al., 2010). It is a space soaked with the antagonism specific to human society (Bedorf, 2010, p. 22; Mouffe, 2005, p. 9). In our times, the adjective *political* and its substantive form used in this text are often viewed as pejorative, but it is time to claim the importance of reaffirming political “as the heart of democratic decision-making” (Hess, 2009, p.38).

On the other side, politics could be considered as the set of forms and solutions that allows common life in the polis. These forms and solutions are the result of decisions and choices which could, but should not, derive from a compromise or a dialogue between the different perspectives present in the political. These forms and solutions shape the institutional structure and the functioning of the polis. In a democracy politics are always evolving and should not be seen as an achieved result, but as a goal to continuously achieve (Weißeno et al., 2010, p. 39).

Politics could be identified as the field of civic instruction and political as the one of education for citizenship and for democracy. The first one targets the learning of notions and knowledge on the functioning of the polis, while the second one points the acquirement of the competencies allowing people to interact in the public space which is the political. In our research we focus mostly on the political and therefore on education for citizenship and for democracy. This choice does not deny the complementarity between these forms and the importance of civic instruction in training citizens for the present and for the future. It simply justifies the choice to use the expression education for the political to define the form of citizenship training at the center of this research.

1.2 One concern: different denominations and different responses coming from a wide range of operators

Depending on the language and on the context, the expression ‘Education for the political’ assumes different appellations. In the curricula of the different linguistic regions of Switzerland, different denominations are used to identify it. These are not simple translations of the same concept. In the German speaking part, it is called *Politische Bildung* (Political formation), in the French speaking part it is named *Éducation à la citoyenneté* (Citizenship education) and in the Italian speaking part *Educazione civica alla cittadinanza e alla democrazia* (Education for civic, for citizenship and for democracy). Although this is only mentioned in Italian, in the three cases this domain includes both the acquirement of notions about the functioning of

the State and of the competencies at the base of common life in the society; and it implies also other subjects as for instance Democracy, Human Rights, Digitalization, Sustainable Development.

A look at the neighboring countries allows to extend outside Switzerland these considerations on the multiplicity of appellations and subjects present under the umbrella of citizenship training outside Switzerland. According to Gökbudak und Hedtke (2020, p.23), in Germany, depending on the federal State in Gymnasium there are different denominations as *Politik und Gesellschaft* (politics and society) in Bavaria, *Politik und Wirtschaft* (politics and economy) in Hesse or *Sozialkunde* (social studies) in Saarland or Thuringia. In Austria, in the *Mittelschule* (secondary I) and in *Gymnasium* (secondary II) the denomination *Politische Bildung* (Political formation) is used (RISa, 2023, p. 22; RISb. 2023, p. 26). The same appellation as in the French speaking part of Switzerland is used in France and in the French speaking parts of Belgium. In Italy since September 2020 *Educazione Civica* (Civic Education) has been introduced (MIUR, 2020).

The school's response to the requirements raised by citizenship training is at the origin of various organizational solutions, as found in a comparative study in which the curricula of several European countries were compared (European Commission, 2018). First, citizenship training can be the subject of a branch on its own, positioned in the weekly timetable. This is the case, for example, of secondary I in French-speaking Switzerland, as established by the *Plan d'études Romand* (CIIP, 2010), where citizenship education is a specific branch of the school curriculum. Second, it can be entrusted to one or a few of the subjects taught, as planned for secondary I in the German-speaking part of Switzerland. The *Lehrplan21* (D-EDK, 2014) incorporates students' citizenship skills in the field “Räume-Zeiten-Gesellschaften” (spaces-times-societies). Specificities are present at cantonal level inside the German speaking part, for instance in the Canton of Aargau this domain is called *Räume-Zeiten-Gesellschaft und Politische Bildung*. In the Canton of Ticino citizenship education in Secondary I is anchored in history teaching (Bernasconi et al., 2022;

DECS, 2021). Third, it can be committed to a wider range, or even to all, of the disciplines taught, as a multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary and transversal school subject. This is the case, for instance of Italy, where *Educazione Civica* is conceived as transversal school discipline (MIUR, 2020).

The differences between the ways of organizing citizenship training mentioned above are only apparently formal. Above all, they reflect the variety of conceptions of citizenship that underlie them. They derive from differences in the conceptualization of citizenship and consequently in the objectives set to form the citizens of today and of tomorrow (European Commission, 2018).

1.3 Educating for the political

1.3.1 Competencies for educating for the political

Competencies are present in all branches taught at school. Civic, citizenship and democracy education represent no exception. As for other school areas, competencies in this domain are played out in the fields of motivation, will and affectivity (Weißeno et al., 2010, pp. 16-17). In addition, competencies related to citizenship education have a strong ethical component and involve values (Audigier, 2000, p. 23). They have a normative face, since they involve evaluation and/or decision-making (Massing, 2012, p. 25). They are differentiated between cognitive, social and personal competencies, which implies attitudes and values. According to Hoskins et al. (2008) one needs to have a high level on all these competencies. Cognitive competencies encompass knowledge about the institutions that govern common life, human rights, democratic principles and the current world (Audigier, 2000, p. 22). Massing (2012, p. 24) adds to this category knowledge about the interest groups, the spatial operators, who influence the choices of the community. These competencies are based on conceptual knowledge, which permits to acquire a specific lexis and facilitates the analysis and construction of arguments and student reflection (Massing, 2012, p. 25). Social and personal skills come into play in an autonomous action (Klieme, 2008, p. 20). This action is based on the ability to live with others, to resolve conflicts and to intervene in public debate (Audigier, 2000, pp. 23-24). The ability to live with others, in socially heterogeneous groups, presupposes that the individual is able to respect and appreciate values, culture and history of the other (Klieme & Hartig, 2008, p. 12). This ability requires solidarity, interdependence and the consideration of different scales in the evaluation of the impacts of a choice (Thémines, 2011, p. 161). Conflict resolution and participation in public debate, according to Massing (2012), require the ability to articulate, argue, negotiate and decide, and also the confrontation of points of view, and the mobilization of values (Thémines, 2011, p. 161). This ability is essential to know how to order the points of

one's reasoning, to motivate them, to discuss them and to arrive at a decision or a judgment that can be played out at the local, national and international level.

1.3.2 Civic and citizenship competence frameworks

In 2006, the European Parliament and the Council of the European Union adopted a recommendation on key competencies for lifelong learning (Council of the European Union, 2006). In this recommendation civic competence was listed as one of the key competences to be developed under the EU Lifelong Learning strategy. Following the Commission's Recommendation, which was updated in 2018 (Council of the European Union, 2018), many Member States have started to incorporate civic competence development in their schools' curricula (Hoskins et al., 2014).

At the international level, various frameworks of citizenship and democratic competencies were elaborated during the last decades (for a comparative overview see WeAreEurope, 2016). These frameworks vary across time and space according to the characteristics of the individual cultural reference context, the type of political constitution, the level of economic wealth, the degree of socio-political stability, national cohesion, and peaceful international relations (European Commission, 2018). The models available also differ according to the age of the learner or with respect to the specific competence those models stress. All these factors vary between countries and change over time, making the concept of citizenship fluid. For example, Hoskins et al. (2014) developed a citizenship model based on data from the International Civic and Citizenship Education Study (ICCS), which monitors the level of citizenship skills of young people (aged about 14) in Europe. In this model four dimensions of citizenship are identified (Fig. 1). The values dimension incorporates the norms to which a good citizen should refer to perform his or her civic duty. The participatory attitudes dimension measures the disposition to engage, drawing on the republican civic ideals of participation. The social justice dimension measures the cosmopolitan values of human rights and respect for diversity. It also encapsulates

the respect for the democratic process. The Knowledge and Skills for Democracy dimension transcends the three models and measures the broad range of skills needed to be an active citizen.

Fig. 1: A model of civic competence (Hoskins et al., 2014)

Knowledge & skills for democracy

Ideally measures the knowledge and skills needed for active citizenship which are wide ranging. It builds on all three models; higher level of knowledge, skills from the civic republican model; emphasis on critical thinking from the critical model; and is influenced by liberal market emphasis on basic skills of reading literacy and ability to take autonomous decisions.

4

1

Citizenship values

Measures the norms regarding the concept of a good citizen. They include questions on engagement in diverse activities from the more traditional voting to the less conventional protest activities. The dimension draws more heavily on civic republican traditions in terms of the conceptions of civic duty.

2

Participatory attitudes

Measures the intention to engage and political self-efficacy. The types of activities covered are broad. The dimension draws more from the civic republican traditions of the importance of citizenship engagement. However, this is broader than national policies and also includes critical citizenship aspects of protest and liberal activities such as volunteering.

3

Social Justice

Measures the beliefs in equal opportunities, equal rights and the democratic process. It draws predominantly from critical citizenship and cosmopolitan values of human rights and respecting equality and diversity. In addition, it draws on the liberal values of respecting the democratic process.

The results of their study suggest that social justice values and students' knowledge and skills for citizenship are promoted particularly in the Nordic system, which combines stable democracy with economic prosperity and democracy-based educational systems where teachers prioritize the promotion of independent and autonomous critical thinking in citizenship education. In contrast, newer democracies with a civic and republican tradition, such as Italy and Greece, for example, achieve more positive results in terms of civic values and participatory attitudes. This is also the case in some recent ex-communist countries that have preserved ethnic notions of citizenship. However, the model of Hoskins et al. (2008) does not cover (due to

lack of data) the civic republican qualities of solidarity and the critical citizenship qualities of empathy and care, that could be found in other frameworks.

Another, more generic framework, which recalls some key (multifunctional and transversal) civic and citizenship competencies, skills and abilities, is the European Framework for Personal, Social and Learning to Learn Key Competence (LifeComp). In this framework critical thinking, collaboration, and empathy are listed as key competences for living in the present world (Sala et al., 2020).

Among all framework of competencies that exist, there is one that has the merit of being able to synthesize paradigms developed in multiple nations, to be valid for all ages and to serve as a reference for learning outside the school context as well. This is the "Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture (RFCDC)" developed by the Council of Europe (2018). It is divided into twenty key competencies and is graphically presented as a flower with four petals (Fig. 2): values, attitudes (the so-called mindset), skills (knowing how to do, knowing how to apply what one knows), knowledge, and critical understanding (what one knows and knows about). According to this model, citizenship skills are based on knowledge of institutions and their functioning, the historical, social and political processes underlying them, and phenomena of importance to the present and future of the planet (see, for example, respect for human rights, climate and demographic changes). Grafted onto this knowledge is the ability to confront, engage and collaborate with others to achieve a common or public interest (i.e. civic mindedness, responsibility, tolerance, openness to cultural otherness and to other beliefs), and all those personal characteristics that contribute to critical and analytical thinking (of the self, of language and communication, of the world) and to the development of a democratic culture (Council of Europe, 2018).

Fig. 2: The 20 competences included in the Reference Framework of Competences for Democratic Culture (Council of Europe, 2018)

1.3.3 Critical thinking, decentration and argumentation and anti-bias attitudes

This Section takes into account works centered on some competencies seen as efficient for educating for the political, considered as a space where different points of view, opinions meet. The considered works are more connected with this project. Educating for the political means giving the opportunity to acquire and strengthen those attitudes, capacities, capabilities, skills and competencies necessary to act in this space.

According to Frech and others (Frech et al., 2020, p. 9) the aim of the education for the political is to promote people's maturity so that they are able to contribute to common life in the society and to critically shape Democracy. They (Frech et al., 2020, p. 9) stress the role of critical thinking and of the capacity to judge and to act as a basis for stability and for the functioning of Democracy. Critical thinking becomes

thus an important competence to be strengthened and deepened in the education for the political.¹

Critical thinking is a “self-adjusting process of judging what to believe or what to do in a given context”, it is therefore connected with acting and judging (Ennis, 1987, p. 10; Facione, 2000, p. 65). Critical thinking should consequently orient, as underlined by Frech and others (2020), the formation towards taking decisions, and solving conflicts. Therefore, education for the political should be based on the principles of problem-oriented teaching and on learning/teaching activities based on the treatment of controversies or political controversial questions, defined as “...authentic questions about the kinds of public policies that should be adopted to address public problems” (Hess, 2009, p. 5). In order to analyze, interpret, explain and evaluate controversial situations students should mobilize their inference skills, defined as “the critical thinking skill that identifies and secures the elements needed to draw reasonable conclusions” (Facione & Gittens, 2013, p. 315). They should also assume a self-regulative attitude, which allows them to evaluate “one's own inferential judgments with a view toward questioning, confirming, validating, or correcting either one's reasoning or one's result” (Facione & Gittens, 2013, p. 315). This implies the competence to decentrate, as defined by Piaget (see Muller Mirza et al., 2009, see also Section 3). Dealing with controversies involves argumentation, an essential ability in a work based on critical thinking (Gaussel, 2016, p. 7).

The efficiency of a toolkit depends on its capacity to mobilize the components of those competences, in particular critical thinking, decentration and argumentation.

Critical thinking and its self-regulating skill, and primarily decentration and argumentation demand the capacity to consider other people's point of view, their way of looking at a conflictual situation. Anti-bias attitudes play an important role in

¹ Therefore, in Section 3 of the present Literature review, we devote an analysis to argumentation studies, which are traditionally related to critical thinking in social interaction.

assuming such a position, since it is impossible to be able to consider someone else's point of view as equally valid as our own if we are negatively biased towards those people. Anti-bias can be defined as an intersectional approach which takes into account the different forms of discrimination as expression of unequal social positions and power relations and consider their complex and mutual entanglements (Anti-Bias-Netz, 2016, p. 11), they are used within anti-discrimination activities (Göthe, 2016, p. 133). It is a concept that impacts on proactive practice and that is critical towards discrimination and conscientious of diversity which reflects the vision of a society aware of prejudices, critical towards discrimination and sensitive of power (Anti-Bias-Netz, 2016, p. 11). This approach has been developed in the 1980s by Louise Derman-Sparks and Carol Brunson-Phillips (Jens, 2010), specifically its origins are in the pedagogy for small children at the Pacific Oaks College in California (Fleischer, 2016, p. 2). Its premises are in the 'Diskriminierungsmodell', which is based on psychology, sociology and philosophy and integrates approaches as gender/queer studies, whiteness studies or post-colonial studies and the model of the interiorized dominance/repression (Fleischer, 2016, p. 4). In the 1990s, after the end of the Apartheid, this approach has been developed by south African pedagogues (Fleischer, 2016, p. 2). The aim of the application of anti-bias approaches in South Africa was the overcoming of apartheid in the heads of people (Anti-Bias-Netz, 2016, p. 12).

1.3.4 Structure of a learning/teaching activity in education for the political

Several methodologies are applied in activities aiming to train, form and educate to citizenship. Usually a learning/teaching activity aiming the education for the political includes the following phases:

- Introductory phase (Frech et al., 2020; Scholz, 2020) with the launching of the chosen controversial subject. In this phase it could be useful to use a triggering element (Hertig, 2012, p. 56) which should turn on the interest of the students, let

come up their precognitions and representations on the controversial subject and awaken questions and a problematization.

- Information and analysis, in which students collect information, deepen their knowledge on the chosen subject, and define its different aspects and the various visions on it. In this phase students learn mostly independently and work individually or in groups. The introductory phase could be considered as a part of this one (Raiser & Warkalla, 2011).
- Application phase in which the controversial subject is handled. In this phase students expose the result of the previous one and develop their argumentations on the controversial subject (Raiser & Warkalla, 2011).
- Evaluation phase (Raiser & Warkalla, 2011), in which the work in the previous phases is evaluated with the aim to define the learnings acquired thanks to these activities. This phase is usually carried out in four steps: intuitive analysis of what happened during the activity; a reflection aimed to explain what happened; the transfer to the reality to understand the relevance of the management-play on the way reality is perceived; critic of the activity focused on acquired learnings (Raiser & Warkalla, 2011, p. 11).

Despite their attribution to one precise phase a lot of methods spread their influence on more phases if not on every phase. Moreover, some of the methods can be combined to and adopted in the same learning/teaching sequence. For instance, the methodologies future workshop (Frech et al., 2020) or argumentations' map (Scholz, 2020, p. 34) require the conduction of activities aimed to collect information and to analyze them, all triggered with a method thought for introducing the subject.

2 Toolkits for educating for the political

After a reflection on the concept of citizenship, its formation, and the competences at the center of citizenship education, the second part of this text focuses on the toolkit used for educating to the political. Section 2.1 focuses on the different

concepts used to define teaching tools and instruments. The following Sections bring on some tools and methods which can be used for educating to the political. In particular Section 2.2 focuses on role-, simulation- and management- plays, Section 2.3 on anti-bias approaches and Section 2.4 on politically controversial questions.

2.1 Untangling a jungle of near-synonyms

Several terms are used in scientific literature to define the elements supporting a learning/teaching activity. These terms include, among others : instrument, tool, approach, method, format, methodology and toolkit.

An instrument or tool could be defined as a simple technology which allows to process information and to transform it in knowledge (Thémines, 2011, p. 54). Referring to geography, maps, images fixed or in movement, the landscape, statistical data, texts are to be considered as instruments. Instruments give students the opportunity to elaborate information about a specific subject in order to build knowledge about it.

A learning/teaching method or approach could be delineated as a form and a procedure allowing teachers and learners to cope with their natural and social surroundings under contemplation of an existing institutional frame (Meyer, 2002, p. 109). Methods can be categorized in function of the role played by learners in the construction of knowledge, from spectators of a show played by the teacher to actors of their own improvement. On the one side, there are the so-called classical learning/teaching methods as lectures intercalated sometimes by questions, while on the other side we have active learning as cooperative learning in which learners are actors and the teacher plays the role of a guide.

A toolkit combines the applications of one or more methods with the use of one or more instruments. Many of these are based on the treatment of controversial subjects. The scientific literature in the French speaking areas use the expression 'questions sociale(ment)s vives' which could be translated with: 'social(ly) acute questions' and could be defined as "a topic that generates debate in the referential

scholarly knowledge, in society and families, and/or at school and in its practices” (Lupatini, 2018, p.2; Lupatini, 2021). Hess (2009) speaks of ‘controversial political questions’ and defines them as “questions of public policy that spark significant disagreement” (Hess, 2009, p. 37) and as she writes they demand “deliberation among a ‘we’ to determine which policy is the best response to a particular problem” (Hess, 2009, p. 37.). Politically controversial questions, issues or topics, as we will conceptualize them, combining the conceptualization utilized in French speaking areas and the one used by Hess, imply a large range of answers which can be also contradictory. School does not only have the right but also the duty to create environments of intellectual and political freedom where it is possible to discuss politically controversial questions and consider different opportunities (Hess, 2009, p. 6) and a tight bond connects discussion on politically controversial questions and the state of health of a democracy (Hess, 2009, p. 12). There are three reasons that make schools prime sites for working on politically controversial questions: 1. opportunities present in the curricula, 2. the presence of a teacher who can teach how to handle them, 3. the ideological diversity of schools (Hess, 2009, p. 22). Research from the 1970s demonstrates the benefit of handling politically controversial questions for fostering civic engagement (Hess, 2009, p. 28) and research on the “development of democratic values provides strong support for the inclusion of controversial issues in democratic education (Hess, 2009, p.31), because they “are authentic, contemporary and open” (Hess, 2009, p. 39). This teaching method permits also to further collective and cooperative learning (Floro, 2011): to educate pupils to respect each other's point of view (Kelly, 1986); to build pupils’ informed opinions and reinforced statements (Albe, 2009); to acquire the competencies of complex and systemic thinking (Albe, 2009; Tutiaux-Guillon, 2006); to develop pupils’ autonomy and responsibility (Simonneaux & Legardez, 2011), to allow a commitment with the “public genres constitutive of the society” (De Pietro and Gagnon, 2013, p. 176); finally to introduce a form of teaching which is no longer based on the leading role of the teacher because it leaves space for negotiating with pupils the organization of learning/teaching activities, and it confers them an active

role in the construction of knowledge, and in modeling teaching/learning experiences in the sense of a more dynamic pedagogy (Albe, 2009, p. 191).

2.2 Role-, simulation- and management-plays

It is possible to differentiate between different formats to plan a learning/teaching activity in the field of education for the political, in which students play as actors and are not simple spectators. The most famous are role-plays, simulation-plays and management-plays. The terms simulation-, role- and management- play are often used as synonyms, although they do not define the same format (Raiser & Warkalla, 2011, p. 9).

In role-plays students usually personify an individual, the activity is therefore less structured (Raiser & Warkalla, 2011, p. 9). In a management-play students simulate a conflict between different groups of interest, the activity is more structured (Raiser & Warkalla, 2011, p. 9). Both role-plays, and management-plays aim to represent and reproduce reality, although this objective is not so central in management-plays as in simulation-plays, consequently critics of management-plays affirm that they allow only a limited representation of the chosen environment (Raiser & Warkalla, 2011, p. 9), but in the center of management-plays stays the pressure of decision-making (Raiser & Warkalla, 2011, p. 10).

It is possible to differentiate two types of management-plays, depending on their focus: knowledge or competence. Knowledge concerns the process of the conflictual chosen situation, its contents or its institutional procedures. Focused competences are interactive/communicative, systemic, action/decision (Raiser & Warkalla, 2011, p. 14). Other criteria can be used to differentiate management-plays: realistic-fictive; orientated towards action or negotiation; complexity level, heterogeneous-homogenous groups of actors (Raiser & Warkalla, 2011, pp. 17-20).

Management-play are appropriate to foster a negotiation aptitude, teamwork, compromise skills, this means social and action competences (Raiser & Warkalla,

2011), it is relevant to remind that management-plays permit the achievement of a reduced number of goals, and that these cannot be reached simultaneously. Moreover, they depend on the attitude of the group using them, this makes their issues unpredictable. Finally, they have to be linked with the general context of the teaching in which they are inserted otherwise students will not understand the need to act during the game (Raiser & Warkalla, 2011, p. 26).

2.3 The anti-bias approach in the teaching/learning process

Sometimes simulation, role or decision plays can be based on an anti-bias approach (Emmert, 2011; Jens, 2010). They are nowadays present at different levels from kindergarten to university and adult education, including also development cooperation and social work (Fleischer, 2016, p. 3). It should also be considered as an important tool in educating for Human Rights (Emmert, 2011) and for avoiding institutionalized racist discrimination (Jens, 2010). Even peacebuilding demands to be aware of the bias present in the society and in the individual and to foster a sense of responsibility toward the other and to develop an accepting attitude (Bickmore, 2004, p. 80). Ant-bias approaches aim to challenge the influence of institutional racist discourses and their implicitness (Jens, 2010, p. 24). Consequently, they play an important role in training for citizenship, because of its potentiality in “un-learning of oppressive and discriminating forms of communication and interaction” (Emmert, 2011, p. 353).

Anti-bias approach includes both the individual level with personal representations and the social level with the societal power structures (Emmert, 2011, p. 353; Jens, 2010, p. 21). It is based on critic of the dominant culture perspectives and representations which prescribe acceptable ways of life; on critic of multicultural approaches considered as inadequate if based on a static conception of culture and reducing cultural specificities to folkloristic aspects which have to be shown in

specific celebration days; and critic colorblind attitudes which emanate from equal treatment of everyone and denies the differences in conditions of life, structural discrimination and unequal distributions of privileges (Fleischer, 2016, p. 3).

From childhood, everyone starts a process of appropriation of stereotypes and prejudices and of affirmation of the difference between oneself and others (Fleischer, 2016, p. 3). This process could lead to discrimination, which has its seeds in assessing differences between humans and in putting them into a hierarchy. If these processes are activated by actors on the base of their power, we have discrimination (Fleischer, 2016, p. 4), which is consequently not caused by differences or individual prejudices, but it is the result of a social construction (Fleischer, 2016, p. 4). As stated by Emmert (2011) “Prejudices and discriminations are not individual misjudgments, but institutionalized in society as ideologies, which are assimilated by everyone. Correspondingly, the behavior based on those prejudices can be un-learned, and institutionalized oppressive ideologies can be discovered, questioned, and analyzed” (p. 353). This approach assumes that everyone has prejudices, and these cannot be unlearned, consequently it does not aim a prejudices-free attitude, it is rather oriented on a prejudices-conscious one (Anti-Bias-Netz, 2016, p. 17). Indeed, the aim of an anti-bias approach is not overcoming prejudices, but a conscious handling of them, this allows another positioning than mortification or overconfidence towards discrimination (Fleischer, 2016, p. 4). To hit this target, anti-bias approaches are based on the sensitization of different forms of discrimination, this by creating spaces of critical reflection and a behavior conscientious of its prejudices (Anti-Bias-Netz, 2016, p. 11). Conscience of one’s own potency and impotence and of one’s own area of influence enables one to assume responsibility for one’s own action (Anti-Bias-Netz, 2016, p. 17).

An anti-bias approach should question our perceptions and assessments and lead to a new inter-personal handling based on parity (Fleischer, 2016, p. 3). The goal of an anti-bias approach is to make visible the slants coming from prejudices and favors

and to dismantle discrimination (Anti-Bias-Netz, 2016, p. 11). According to Louise Derman-Sparks its objectives are:

- “The recognition and empowerment of all those involved in learning processes in their individual and reference group identities;
- The promotion of a respectful and appreciative attitude towards diversity among people;
- Raising awareness of prejudice and discrimination and support of critical thinking;
- Encouraging and strengthening the ability to act against discrimination" (Anti-Bias-Netz, 2016, p. 13).

Anti-bias approaches are efficient for educating for the political first because they focus on power relations and on fostering competences which promote a conscious handling with its own power and impotence (Fleischer, 2016, p. 4). Second, they do not focus on sentiments of guilt with the situation, but on sensing and experiencing its own involvement with power relationships and to recognize the effects of inequalities in the societies on oneself and on the others (Fleischer, 2016, p. 8). They are lifelong processes including both trainers as learners (Fleischer, 2016, p. 4). Nevertheless, they do not offer a recipe for democracy, but opportunities for a lifelong work on attitudes conscious of the diversities (Fleischer, 2016, p. 7) and in our times in which inequalities and extremism strongly grow and simple black and white schematics influence more and more the political debates it is important to support an education for the political able to take into account the complexity of societal balances of power without losing its capacity of acting (Fleischer, 2016, p. 8).

Fleischer (2016, p. 7) describes different ways to apply anti-bias approaches to educate adults for the political. She distinguishes between development processes focused on staff and courses for specific occupational groups.

As examples for the first type of approach, she brings a three-year project hold in Freiburg i. B. in the frame of the German Federal program “Toleranz fördern - Kompetenz stärken” (foster tolerance - strengthen competence) and the project

“Perspektivewechsel” (perspective change) conducted by the Welfare center of Jews in Germany.

As examples for the second type, she brings two days anti-bias workshops for groups between 8 and 12 persons, held by two persons, or courses which can take from 8 to 10 days, for instance for the preparation and the follow-up of foreign operations. Often the workshops organizers introduce elements of working inspired by theater or other creatives methods.

Fleischer (2016, p. 7) also describes a concrete procedure of anti-bias training. At the beginning there are simple and not too personal questions about the situation of the people involved. This is because involvement with its own balance of power is considered difficult both for offenders and for victims. In the second phase, the focus is on prejudices; namely, first on the prejudices the participants know or believe other people have on them, then on the ones participants have on other people. This allows us to understand that life without prejudices is not realistic, but that it is possible to deal consciously with them. In a third phase the focus is on its own societal positioning. In this phase participants individually name the differentiations they consider as important. Later, in a group or plenum interaction, participants discuss how it feels to be part of the winners or of the losers in society, and on the lines of differences considered as important. This should help participants to gain awareness of their privileged position. Meanwhile the leaders of the workshop underline vehemently the contradiction between naming categories and criticize them. In the following phase participants are asked which differentiation lines could be concretely present in the seminar, and how they act. This opens the door to a discussion on balances of power and power relationships. This shows that power dynamics are present even in the group. On these premises it is possible to discuss and establish rules for the functioning of the group.

Kontzi and Mamutovič (2016, pp. 35-43) stress the importance of human rights education since the first school years, this because studies demonstrate that discrimination happens in schools often and systematically and this affects students'

self-conscience and their results. They see critical thinking as an essential competence for human rights education because it permits a consciousness-raising of prejudices and bias, to listen to other one's opinion and to express its own. They stress that prejudices are not innate. Children acquire them with the observation of their environment, and by evaluating external marks, balances of power and the resulting privileges, this affects their behavior towards other people. Kontzi and Mamutovič (2016, p. 39) define the objectives of an anti-bias approach with children as follows:

1. Strengthen own identity and the one towards own reference groups;
2. Develop respect and empathy for diversity;
3. Encourage critical thinking towards prejudices and discrimination;
4. Stand up against prejudices and discrimination.

They stress how prejudices are present in schools and they give the example of how proscribing children to speak their mother language at school affects the development of their identity and the one of their reference groups, this is against the first objective of an anti-bias approach with children (Kontzi & Mamutovič, 2016, p. 41). To conclude their text, they name some changes which could help schools diminish prejudices and discrimination.

Göthe (2016) works on empowerment and on critical whiteness studies and compares them with anti-bias approaches. She led a group and an individual interview with two experts for each of the named fields (Göthe, 2016, p. 128). In a work with empowerment, critical whiteness and anti-bias the concepts power-sharing, ethical handling with privileges and alliances play a central role (Göthe, 2016, p. 137).

Empowerment-approach is an important instrument for organizing politically a collectivity, for developing a collective culture of conscious resistance against inequality, racism and oppression and for strengthening self-determination and participation (Göthe, 2016, p. 131).

Critical whiteness studies focus both on people with experienced racism and on white positioning in political power structures, their advantages and privileges (Göthe, 2016, p. 131).

An anti-bias approach should be based on relationships that are the starting points for the development of joint action and potential solidarity, based on trust and confrontation (Göthe, 2016, p. 138).

All three approaches are based on social utopias. Empowerment sets the focus on the individual and their needs and exposes collective structures in society that promote violence with the aim of changing them. The critical whiteness approach is based on power sharing, with the aim of unmasking discrimination. The anti-bias approach drafts the vision of a prejudice-conscious, power- and discrimination-critical society (Göthe, 2016, p. 138). The capacity to construct utopias is a central pillar in education for the political, because it pushes not only to believe in changes but also to acting for making them possible (Göthe, 2016, p. 140).

2.4 Politically controversial questions in the teaching/learning processes.

It is important to stress that “conflict and its management are basic to democracy” (Bickmore, 2004, p. 77), because if “there is no controversy there is no democracy” (Hess, 2009, p. 162) and “you cannot have democracy without discussion” (Hess, 2009, pp. 15-16). Therefore, conflict management is considered as central in many learning/teaching activities aimed to educate for the political. Conflict management and resolution-based activities are focused mostly on peacemaking and peacebuilding approaches (Bickmore, 2004, p. 77). Peacemaking attempts to manage conflicts through dialogue and problem-solving, it promotes the ability to act or to choose how to act (Bickmore, 2004, p. 79) and peacebuilding “adds long-range harm reduction through social reconstruction” (Bickmore, 2004, p. 77) and focuses on “rebuilding equitable and resilient relationships at any point in the conflict cycle” (Bickmore, 2004, p. 80).

Hess (2009, pp. 53-76) presents three good examples of teaching based on handling controversial political issues. She details the three good examples. The first teacher had the purpose of strengthening the capacity of considering multiple perspectives of the proposed issue. The second focused on promoting students' critical thinking, considering it important for its development "to take a different position and to argue it with credence and credibility" (Hess, 2009, p. 63). The third one aimed at improving students' abilities to discuss controversial political issues.

The first teacher used the model of Town Meeting "a large group discussion in which each participant assumes the role of a person with a particular perspective" (Hess, 2009, p. 57). For the discussions the second teacher chose a model labeled as seminar "a text-based, large group discussion designed to help participant develop a deeper understanding of the issues, ideas and values in the text (Hess, 2009, p. 61). The third teacher applied the Public Issues Model which "uses three specific types of questions (factual, definitional and value-oriented) to guide the discussion of larger public policy issues" (Hess, 2009, p. 67).

Hess (2009: 77-95) relates also a study conducted between 2005 and 2008 in 35 classes in 21 high schools in IL, IN and WI. The study has a mixed-method with surveys analyzed quantitatively and classroom observations and interviews with students and teachers analyzed quantitatively. The study focused on the ideological diversity both inside the classes (inter-personal diversity) and inside the person (intra-personal diversity). From the study emerges that students want to hear different views mostly if "the discussion provided adequate time and the expectation that students explain their views, not just state them" (Hess, 2009, p. 84). This promotes "open mindedness and the willingness to engage in political discussions outside of the classroom" (Hess, 2009, p. 80).

3 An argumentative perspective on education to a dynamic citizenship

Given the importance of dialogue on controversial issues, critical thinking and conflict management, which has emerged in the previous Sections, our Literature review will now complement the political and educational approaches discussed above with insights coming from the tradition of argumentation studies. This latter is focused on an exchange of arguments happening in a dialogical (social) context, ideally orientated towards a reasonable resolution of disagreement. In Section 3.1, we will discuss the main definition of argumentation. Section 3.2 narrows down the focus, and considers argumentation in the domain of education, which is central for the TEDYC project. In particular, while Section 3.2.1 discusses argumentation studies related to education to citizenship (3.2.1), Section 3.2.2 focuses on pedagogical interventions related to the design of argumentative spaces. A relevant sub-Section (3.2.2.1) considers online platforms and tools for argumentation visualization, emphasizing in particular how some of these tools have been created with the explicit aim to enable better deliberation and, in some cases, education to citizenship.

3.1 Definition of argumentation as a dialogic activity promoting reasonable exchange

As a discipline, the roots of argumentation are related to ancient rhetorical and dialectical tradition, dating back to Aristotle as concerns the Western tradition. Such tradition developed through the Latin times and Middle Ages, to be then partially lost in continental Europe after the humanist renaissance and rediscovered later on in modern and contemporary studies, after both Toulmin (1958) and Perelman & Olbrechts-Tyteca (1958) famously published their work in the aftermath of the Second World War. The story of the tradition of argumentation is partially different in the English-speaking countries, in which rhetoric and the education to public debate remained active throughout history, with universities and other educational

institutions maintaining the argumentative tradition of debate (see for example Ziegelmüller & Kay, 1997), which nowadays revived in different countries, including Switzerland.

Presently, different approaches converge in argumentation studies. Some approaches tend to be more *monological* (Schwarz & Baker, 2017, pp. 68ff) and centered on argumentation as a *product* of individual reasoning: generally speaking, these approaches focus on arguments as inferential moves, i.e., as inferential connections between premises and a conclusion that is defended through argumentation. Other approaches are *dialogical*, meaning that argumentation is considered as a *process* and not as a product. The focus of these approaches is on the activity of argumentation as a “communicative and interactional act complex aimed at resolving a difference of opinion with the addressee by putting forward a constellation of propositions for which the arguer can be held accountable in order to make the standpoint at issue acceptable to a rational judge who judges reasonably” (van Eemeren, 2018, p. 3). This definition contains several aspects that are widely accepted by dialogical approaches: notably, the idea of a communication *process*, aimed at resolving a disagreement in an ideally reasonable dialogical exchange, in which interlocutors try to resolve their differences by means of weighting the reasons for the different positions (standpoints) at issue. In this sense, argumentation is the intertwining of “mutually influencing discourses” and involves “changes in participants’ ways of interacting and underlying views” (Schwarz & Baker, 2017, p. 73).

Not surprisingly, this idea of argumentation as reasonable exchange of opinion in dialogue has brought several authors to consider public debate and political discussions as key areas in which argumentation plays a role. Authors have equally considered the potential of argumentation as a conflict resolution method, i.e., as an approach that allows to prevent and manage disagreement without making it escalate into overt conflict, or even resolve escalated conflicts (Aakhus, 2003; Greco Morasso, 2011). A positive approach to conflict management is part of an education to a

dynamic citizenship, because it allows participants to *decentrate* from consider their own individual position as the only viable one (Muller Mirza et al., 2009, pp. 70-71) and consider others' points of view in a reasonable discussion, without the need of papering up disagreement or to make it escalate into interpersonal acrimony (Greco, 2018).

All these aspects have to do with an education to dynamic citizenship, because the potential of argumentative dialogue is to foster democratic debate (e.g., Schwarz & Baker, 2017, p. 132,), allowing young students to learn how to deal with disagreement and controversial issues in a dialogic and reasoned way (which, as noted above, is central to an education to a dynamic citizenship).

In the following sections, we will focus on the most important streams of literature that contribute to defining argumentation as a contributing tool for citizens' education. We will first briefly introduce the field of argumentation in education, which is a flourishing area of studies, combining both conceptual and intervention-based research (Sect. 3.2). Within this field, we will then devote particular attention to studies that concern argumentation in areas related to an education to citizenship or civic education (3.2.1), including history, debate and the discussion of controversial issues in the classroom. Because, as said, argumentation in education often includes a reflection on how to create or improve the conditions for students' argumentation in the classroom, we will then focus on the concept of design of argumentation, which is particularly important in this field (Sect. 3.2.2). In Sect. 3.2.2, we will then go through the toolkits that have been produced for experiencing argumentation in the classroom, in different fields but, again, with a focus on studies related to disciplines close to citizenship education. Finally, Sect. 3.2.2.1 takes a somewhat different perspective on the same subject, by focusing on online platforms and tools for argumentation visualization, which have been designed to foster dialogic argumentation exchanges in education and in other contexts. These represent particular kinds of toolkit, given their technological support.

3.2 Argumentation in education

As noted in Sect. 3.1, argumentation studies are in a sense intertwined with public debate and democracy, with many authors dealing with political discussions in various activity types. As mentioned, traditions such as the education to *debate* have always been tightly related to the public training of good citizens in educational systems.

In particular, a significant stream of research on argumentative processes in the past decades has been concentrating on the field of education. In a sense, the tradition of argumentation mentioned in Sect. 3.1 is gradually merging with educational studies, in which the interest for the development of children's argumentation has always been a matter of interest (Larraín & Fortes de Macêdo, 2020).

One of the main areas of interest in the literature on argumentation and education concerns how argumentative skills can be taught to children and how educational systems can improve children's and adolescents' skills (see for example the seminal work by Kuhn, 1991). As Greco & Perret-Clermont (2023, p. 457) put it, "The objective of these approaches is to develop school programs that allow students to develop their critical thinking, to build their minds (Resnick & Schantz, 2015) and to take part in a responsible way in democratic discussions, learning to listen and to be accountable for their own contributions (Littleton & Mercer, 2013)".

In order to develop students' argumentative skills, according to Schwarz and Baker (2017) "arguing to learn has (...) been identified as one of the key processes of social learning in specific teaching domains" (p. xvi). With *arguing to learn* they refer to approaches that "work from the argumentative skills that students already possess, as people already well able to communicate with others" (Schwarz and Baker, 2017, p. xvi), in opposition to "pedagogical approach(es) mainly targeted at the development of high-order thinking skills" (Schwarz and Baker, 2017, p. xvi).

A second area of particular importance for the TEDYC project regards those approaches that concentrate on the *design* of argumentative spaces in educational

settings, i.e., on providing the conditions for children's and adolescents' argumentation to be developed and improved. Given the importance of a design perspective for the effort of creating a toolkit for a dynamic citizenship, we will devote an entire section to these approaches (Sect. 3.2.2).

Many studies focus on the topic of argumentation in science classes. For example, Prusak et al. (2012) present a case study in which a dyad of pupils must solve a mathematical task, in order to show that “a meticulous design can lead pre-service teachers to engage in productive unguided peer argumentation” (Prusak et al., 2012, p. 19). Sampson and Grooms (2009) observe that in order for students to become able to use scientific reasoning, “teachers also need to provide students with numerous opportunities to develop the critical-thinking skills and scientific habits of mind that are needed to assess alternative ideas, weigh evidence, interpret the meaning of texts and evaluate the validity or acceptability of a scientific explanation” (Sampson and Grooms, 2009, p. 66). For this purpose, they propose “an instructional model that science teachers can use to promote and support student engagement in scientific argumentation” (Sampson and Grooms, 2009, p. 66), called “the evaluate alternatives instructional model” (Sampson and Grooms, 2009, p. 66).

In Switzerland, different studies were carried out on argumentation in language classes: Schneuwly (2000) has worked on the teaching of oral language skills, in particular focusing on helping pupils understand different public communication situations and acquire the linguistic skills necessary to express oneself in each of those situations (see Schneuwly, 2000, pp. 55-56). Among these situations there are many that require argumentation skills: Schneuwly mentions in fact as examples of situations “negotiation, participation at a round table” (Schneuwly, 2000, p. 56).

Also in the Swiss context, Dolz and colleagues (2000) propose some tools to be used in teaching “ordered debate” (“débât régulé”, Dolz and colleagues, 2000), in the form of six different teaching modules (Dolz and colleagues, 2000, p. 45). They analyze the progress made by elementary school children after having participated in lessons

employing these tools and they conclude that these are indeed effective in improving pupils' ways of engaging in the practice of debate.

Luginbühl et al. (2022) point out that recent research on the topic of oral argumentation skills in educational contexts highlighted “that oral argumentation is not only a learning objective (‘learning to argue’), but also a way of acquiring knowledge (‘arguing to learn’), see Asterhan and Schwarz 2016; Garcia-Mila et al. 2013; Walker and Sampson 2013; Baker 2009)” (Luginbühl et al., 2022, p. 138). Therefore, they emphasize the need for developing “didactic concepts to train and evaluate oral argumentation skills” (Luginbühl et al., 2022, p. 138). In order to do so, they consider pivotal to have a way to assess oral argumentation skills that takes into account both “the product *and* the process of argumentation; (as) these two perspectives are independent” (Luginbühl et al., 2022, p. 139): they therefore recognize argumentation as a *dialogical* process, in which arguments are co-constructed and influenced by the ongoing discussion, rather than an individual one.

3.2.1 Argumentation and education to citizenship

After having considered a general overview of key aspects regarding the interrelation between argumentation and education, in this section we will focus on the scholarly literature that has considered the specific area of education to citizenship, which is at the core of our project. The potential benefits of an effective education to citizenship are key to acquire fundamental skills: as Akar observes, “in conflict-prone societies, classroom dialogues, critical thinking and collaboration can support the building of competencies for reconciliation, intellectual freedom and social cohesion” (Akar, 2012, p. 471).

Studies in the field have focused both on understanding the limits of contemporary teaching approaches to education to citizenship and on studying the benefits of different novel and alternative teaching methods that allow to (partially) overcome these limits.

For example, Kuhn and colleagues (2019) underline the benefits of having young students address contemporary challenging issues in “a student-centered instructional approach emphasizing peer-to-peer discourse” (Kuhn et al., 2019, p. 207), by showing how the implementation of such an approach for a school year was useful for improving students' skills both in written argumentation and in discourse (Kuhn et al. 2019).

Concerning the limits of current teaching approaches, Rapanta and colleagues (2021) point out that “the practical aspects of being a citizen in its authentic, global, democratic sense are not sufficiently emphasized within current (civic education) curricula” (Rapanta et al., 2021, p. 475). In particular, they argue that a focus on cultural literacy is lacking, in spite of the fact that it would be important in the current socio-political environment in Europe - characterized by constant changes on many levels (Rapanta et al, 2021). To improve this situation, they propose “an innovative citizenship education curriculum based on dialogic, argumentative and cultural literacy skills (...) proposing discursive practices of cultural identity construction at a collaborative level (small group or whole class) inspired by wordless texts (picture books and animated films) on core civic cultural values such as tolerance, empathy and inclusion” (Rapanta et al., 2021, p. 475). They advocate for a citizenship education that allows learners to practice democracy, not (only) through practicing one’s “civic duties (i.e. voting, understanding and following rules” (Rapanta et al., 2021, p. 477), but also by learning and practicing “dialogic empathy” (Rapanta et al., 2021, p. 478): actively listening to the other’s point of view with a genuine interest for *understanding his/her reasoning* and for finding common ground. In particular, it is important that learners accept the idea that “different viewpoints on the same issue may exist and be equally valid” (Rapanta e al. 2021, p. 478).

Another study (Olsen and colleagues 2018) has investigated whether there is a correlation between students’ argumentation skills and their participation in some citizenship education’s teaching activities (such as classroom discussions). They have looked at “the ways in which students create arguments” (Olsen et al. 2018, p.

58) through an analysis of written argumentative essays produced by “a ninth-grade humanities classroom” (Olsen et al. 2018, p. 58), with a particular interest on intertextual connections. The fact that students draw in their written essays from elements that emerged during classroom discussions show that argumentative writing is a social practice, in which students “(took) actions to participate in their community through their writing” (Olsen et al. 2018, p. 83).

3.2.2 The design of argumentation

As mentioned in Sect. 3.2, part of the educational literature on argumentation has concentrated on argumentation *design*, i.e. on the conditions and tools that can be pre-designed in order for students to engage in argumentative activities, which can be offline or mediated by technological tools (see more in Sect. 3.2.2.1; for a review, see Andriessen & Schwarz, 2009). As noted by Greco and Perret-Clermont (2022), an interesting design effort has been developed in the UK by Neil Mercer and colleagues, grouped round the *Thinking together* program. On the basis of an evaluation of different kinds of talk (communicative interaction) and how much they are conducive to reason-based exchange of opinion and learning, they establish some practical rules and practices to share with the students in order to design spaces for discussion in the classroom (Littleton & Mercer, 2013, p. 38). Although these rules were not designed with education to citizenship in mind, they are worth quoting because they are general rules for an exploratory talk (see also the discussion in Greco, 2020).

Andriessen & Schwarz (2009) make some suggestions, building on relevant literature, on the design of argumentative activities in educational settings. In particular, they stress the fundamental role of motivation in argumentative design, explaining that “understanding argument is related to understanding social conflict and goal-directed action” (Andriessen & Schwarz, 2009, p. 147) and therefore “in learning contexts, students will be motivated to engage in argumentation only if they feel

confident about their knowledge being sufficient, and the social challenges are manageable and that they can gain from it” (Andriessen & Schwarz, 2009, p. 148).

Scholars have extensively focused on argumentation in science classrooms. For example, Gonzales and colleagues (2018) designed a toolkit for argumentation in science classrooms, a website that “is organized around two interrelated areas of argumentation that have been shown to be challenging for students: (1) the structural elements of an argument, and (2) student interactions” (McNeil et al. 2016)” (Gonzales et al., 2018, p. 75). As for the second area concerned, they point out that “to support these types of interactions, the classroom environment needs to be a safe space where students feel they can work through their evolving understandings with other students (Reiser, Berland, and Kenyon 2015)” (Gonzales et al., 2018, p. 76).

Micheals and colleagues (2008) present a set of “classroom discussion practices that can lead to reasoned participation by all students” (Micheals et al., 2008, p. 283) under the name of “Accountable Talk SM” (Micheals et al., 2008, p. 283). These practices are meant to prompt students’ *accountability* in terms of: (a) “accountability to the learning community” (Micheals et al., 2008, p. 283), meaning that students are encouraged to both explain their point of view to others and to carefully listening to others with the aim of understanding theirs; (b) “accountability to accepted standards of reasoning”, i.e. how to properly construct and use argumentation, and (c) “accountability to knowledge”, i.e. relying on factual evidence such as written texts to build their arguments and evaluate those of others.

Schuitema and colleagues (2019) developed “two curriculum units for dialogic citizenship education” (Schuitema et al., 2019, p. 439) to promote the inclusion of citizenship education in history classes. Their work relies on the premise that “acquiring domain-specific knowledge and skills cannot be separated from moral development” (Schuitema et al., 2019, p. 440).

In Switzerland, for example, in the Canton of Fribourg, the DSAS (direction de la santé et des affaires sociales) has worked on an action plan for 2018-2021 called “Je

participe!” (“I participate”: <https://www.fr.ch/vie-quotidienne/enfance-jeunesse-et-famille/politique-de-lenfance-et-de-la-jeunesse-je-participe/plan-daction-cantonal-je-participe>), in which one of the objectives is to encourage participation to civic life. Among the interventions they envisage in this document, they mention: “develop social engagement and living together in the education environments, i.e. schools”; “a right to express one’s opinion and to be listened to” to be promoted through “encouraging participative practices”, “developing cantonal structures and projects that favor participation”; “promote civic education” (specifically, by promoting the teaching of debate in schools, by supporting projects and events that promote civic education and by participating to a film festival that gives awards to productions by young people that inspire young generations to use their civic rights: <https://www.fr.ch/etat-et-droit/votations-elections-et-droits-politiques/cinecivic>).

In 2005, the 2nd issue of the magazine “Résonances” (a monthly magazine dedicated to education in the Canton Valais), dedicates four articles to the topic of argumentation and its relevance for civic education, in particular to counter the tendency of living in a society where the “pensée unique” seems to be predominant. They stress that education has a fundamental role “pour l’exercice de la pensée” because “raisonner, argumenter, débattre sont des activités qui permettent d’évoluer vers cette citoyenneté tellement nécessaire pour ne pas se laisser aveugler par une vision ne prenant en compte qu’une seule dimension, alors que la réalité est multidimensionnelle”.

In the Canton of Ticino, the education magazine “Scuola Ticinese” in an issue on the topic of “Listening” dedicates an article on the role of “listening and democracy”, in which Ghiringhelli (2020), a historian, writes that even if perhaps it is not possible to teach democratic participation, it is certainly possible to teach the elements on which democracy is built, namely critical thinking and the ability to judge autonomously^[1], which are intrinsically linked to argumentation and dialogue.

3.2.2.1 Online platforms and tools for argumentation visualization

Among the educational design efforts that have been proposed in the literature (Sect. 3., a field that is growing at a fast pace includes technological tools that facilitate argument visualization. In the past years, these tools have been growing in number and importance and have been integrated in a variety of settings. In this section, we propose a brief overview of some of them. For a more complete list of how these tools were developed, see the overview in Schwarz and Baker (2017, pp. 197ff).

For the purposes of the TEDYC project, it is particularly important to focus on those visualization tools that start from a dialogical view of argumentation (Sect. 3.1) and, therefore, in the words of Muller Mirza et al. (2007), provide “graphical and visual descriptions of arguments that can serve as external references for collective learning or problem solving”. In fact, different tools and discussion platforms may be designed on the basis of very different epistemological and philosophical starting points. Given the focus on an education to dynamic citizenship, it is particularly important to review those tools that do not contradict the basic principles of open discussion.^[2]

While the effort to design platforms and tools has been dramatically increasing in recent years, some tools have been around for quite some time. To start with an example dating back to two decades ago, one could mention the DIGALO application, described in the above-cited paper (Muller Mirza et al., 2007), and developed in the 2000s within the European Consortium DUNES (Dialogical argumentative Negotiation Educational Software).^[3] DIGALO has been used, for example, to foster knowledge of historical controversial issues, which arguably is part of an education to citizenship. Around the same time, the argument mapping software tool Araucaria was developed in 2001 at the University of Dundee, Scotland; this is a case in which the tool is useful to map and analyze the arguments used, even though it was not designed for use in the classroom. The Center for Argument Technology (ARG-Tech, <https://arg-tech.org/>) at the University of Dundee has released advanced argument mapping software tools, such as OVA3, and has participated in a series of initiatives to improve public debate in the UK.

Some technologies and tools are explicitly designed not only to visualize or map arguments but also to help deliberation processes, making them more transparent and inclusive, and enhancing the quality of argumentation. Some examples of these technologies are the following: DebateHub, “an open, online, collaborative tool to support collective ideation, deliberation and democratic decision making” (<https://debatehub.net/>, see Quinto, Iandoli & De Liddo, 2021), BCAUSE, designed for groups to “co-create solutions to complex problems by openly discussing them with others” (<https://bcause.app/home>), or Evidence-Hub, which was designed “to pool, map and harness what a community knows” in order to “understand different perspectives and support quality debates” (<https://evidence-hub.net/>, see De Liddo & Buckingham Shum, 2013).

Finally, the platform Middle Ground (<https://middleground.nl>), originally designed from an idea by Jan Albert van Laar from the University of Groningen in The Netherlands (see van Laar, 2021), is particularly relevant, as it includes a deliberation dimension as well as an explicitly educational dimension. The website of this tool explains that it is designed to encourage “students to cooperate on the joint development of a well-reasoned compromise which could settle a social issue”; hence, it is particularly suited for social and political issues, which are at the core of an education to citizenship. The tool is designed for use “in social studies and civic education in secondary school and secondary vocational education” as well as in higher education. It is designed to be integrated within existing curricula and starts from a positive view of finding a compromise on controversial issues, which is often important in matters of political relevance.

^[1] “forse non è possibile insegnare l’adesione alla democrazia, ma sicuramente si possono insegnare i caratteri fondanti su cui poggia la democrazia, in primis l’esercizio dello spirito critico e dell’autonomia di giudizio”. Ghiringhelli (2020).

^[2] It is to be noted that, given the sophistication of current tools, some of them raise concern about what kind of educational and societal value they may have. A critical view of what platforms and technologies offer is always important. To cite a recent example, the AI powered negotiation tool delivered by Meta (the parent company of Facebook), not specifically for educational purpose but as

a diplomatic game, has been at the center of controversial debate for its potentially negative uses (see <https://www.washingtonpost.com/technology/2022/12/01/meta-diplomacy-ai-cicero/>). We are grateful to our colleague Anna De Liddo for sharing these considerations.

^[3] <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/IST-2001-34153>

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